

REVIEW OF POSSIBLE THREATS AND SOLUTIONS FOR INFORMATION SECURITY ON INTERNET

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ABSTRACT

In today's world, business and individuals demand instant communication ability and for this internet communication is the vastly used media. The communication over internet has various security concerns associated with it because the information that is provided by the user of the internet may fall in unsafe hands and could cause a great damage to an individual or may result in huge losses for a business organization. The present paper provides a brief overview of various threats related to information security on internet. Various hacking techniques have been categorized and the impact of hacking on internet infrastructure has been elaborated. State-of-the-art technologies used for security of information have been discussed in the present paper. The paper concludes by giving precautionary guidelines that must be followed while information disclosure on internet is being made.

Keywords: *Hacking, DNS hacking attacks, Denial of Service attacks, Biometrics, Cryptography, Digital Signatures*

1. INTRODUCTION

Computers permeate every aspect of modern life and business. They have found extensive use in both the public and private sectors. Apart from their traditional use in terms of storage/retrieval, computers are used increasingly to make decision and trusted to control important operations without human supervision. Obviously, the potential for mischief is enormous if such systems are tempered with illicitly.

Illicit tempering of computer systems (computer misuse) takes many forms and the most common are probably hacking and computer viruses. Hacking generally refers to activity of gaining unauthorized access to a computer system or network. Computer viruses generally refer to programs which replicate themselves, delete stored information or alter the stored information from the infected computer. Hacking is often the first step in a computer misuse instance. Once a hacker has managed to gain unauthorized entry to a computer system he or she can then try to reprogram the system, delete or modify the data contained therein.

The present paper deals with the various threats related to information security. The paper has been divided into various sections. Sections-2 introduces the various types of hacking attacks which can be physical, Syntactic and Semantic.

Various hacking techniques like Trojan programs, phishing, spoofing etc. have also been discussed. Section-3 introduces the 'impact of hacking activities on internet infrastructure'. Section-4 introduces the state of the art technologies for information security which uses modern tools likes Biometric security solutions, Honey Pot Decoys and Padded Cells, Tokens and Cryptography. For computer application in which a user must access multiple resources, biometrics can greatly simplify the authentication process. Section-5 highlights the precautionary guidelines for information disclosure on the internet. Section-6 concludes the paper and also presents the future work in this field.

2. TYPES OF HACKING ATTACK

Galley [1] discusses three types of attacks against computer systems: Physical, Syntactic and Semantic. A physical attack uses conventional weapons, such as bombs or fire.

A syntactic attack uses virus-type software to disrupt or damage a computer system or network. A semantic attack is a more subtle approach. Its goal is to attack users' confidence by causing a computer system to produce errors and unpredictable results.

Syntactic attacks are sometimes grouped under the term "malicious software" or "malware".

These attacks may include viruses, worms, and Trojan horses. One common vehicle of delivery for malware is email.

Semantic attacks involve the modification of information or dissemination of incorrect information [2]. Modification of information has been perpetrated even without the aid of computers, but computers and networks have provided new opportunities to achieve this.

Also, the dissemination of incorrect information to large numbers of people quickly is facilitated by such mechanisms as email, message boards, and websites [3].

Types of Internet Hacking [4,5]

Hacking tricks can be divided into different categories:

1. Trojan programs that share files via instant messenger.
2. Phishing
3. Fake Websites.
4. Spoofing
5. Spyware
6. Electronic Bulletin Boards
7. Information Brokers

8. Internet Public Records
9. Malicious Applications: Trojan Horses

2.1 Trojan programs that share files via instant messenger

Instant messaging allows file-sharing on a computer [6]. All present popular instant messengers have file sharing abilities, or allow users to have the above functionality by installing patches or plug-ins; this is also a major threat to present information security. These communication software's also make it difficult for existing hack prevention methods to prevent and control information security.

Hackers use instant communication capability to plant Trojan program into an unsuspected program; the planted program is a kind of remotely controlled hacking tool that can conceal itself and is unauthorized. The Trojan program is unknowingly executed, controlling the infected computer; it can read, delete, move and execute any file on the computer. The advantages of a hacker replacing remotely installed backdoor Trojan programs [7] with instant messengers to access files are: When the victim gets online, the hacker will be informed. Thus, a hacker can track and access the infected computer, and incessantly steal user information. Certain Trojan programs are designed especially for instant messengers.

These Trojans can change group settings and share all files on the hard disk of the infected computer. They can also destroy or modify data, causing data disarray. This kind of program allows a hacker access to all files on an infected computer, and thus poses a great threat to users. The Trojan program takes up a large amount of the resources of the computer causing it to become very slow and often crashes without a reason. Trojan programs are Backdoor Trojan, AIMVision, and Backdoor. Sparta.C. Backdoor Trojans use ICQ pager to send messages to its writer. AIMVision steals AIM related information stored in the Windows registry, enabling a hacker to setup an AIM user id. Backdoor. Sparta.C uses ICQ to communicate with its writer and opens a port on an infected host and sends its IP Address to the hacker and at the same time attempts to terminate the antivirus program or firewall of the host.

2.1.1 Hijacking and Impersonation

There are various ways through which a hacker can impersonate other users [8]. The most commonly used method is eavesdropping on unsuspecting users to retrieve user accounts, passwords and other user related information.

Hackers wishing to obtain user accounts may do so with the help of Trojans designed to steal passwords. If an instant messenger client stores his/her password on his/her computer, then a hacker can send a Trojan program to the unsuspecting user. When the user executes the program, the program shall search for the user's password and send it to the hacker.

There are several ways through which a Trojan program can send messages back to the hacker.

The methods include instant messenger, IRC, e-mails, etc. Current four most popular instant messengers are AIM, Yahoo! Messenger, ICQ, and MSN Messenger, none of which encrypts its flow. Therefore, a hacker can use a man-in-the-middle attack to hijack a connection, then impersonate the hijacked user and participate in a chat-session. Although difficult, a hacker can use the man-in-the-middle attack to hijack the connection entirely.

2.1.2 Denial of Service (DoS)

There are many ways through which a hacker can launch a denial of service (DoS) attack [9] on an instant messenger user. A Partial DoS attack will cause a user end to hang, or use up a large portion of CPU resources causing the system to become unstable. However, a hacker can use tools that allow him to log in using several different identities at the same time, or automatically create a large number of new user ids, thus enabling a flood attack. Once a flood attack begins, even if the user realizes that his/her computer has been infected, the computer will not be able to respond. Thus, the problem cannot be solved by putting a hacker's user id on the ignore list of your instant messenger.

DoS attacks are very easy to generate and very difficult to detect, and hence are attractive weapons for hackers. In a typical DoS attack, the attacker node spoofs its IP address and uses multiple intermediate nodes to overwhelm other nodes with traffic. DoS attacks are typically used to take important servers out of action for a few hours, resulting in DoS for all users served by the server. It can also be used to disrupt the services of intermediate routers.

2.1.3 Information Disclosure

Retrieving system information through instant messenger users is currently the most commonly used hacking tool [10]. It can effortlessly collect user network information like, current IP, port, etc. IP address retriever is an example. IP address retrievers can be used to many purposes; for instance, a Trojan when integrated with an IP address retriever allows a hacker to receive all information related to the infected computer's IP address as soon as the infected computer connects to the internet.

Therefore, even if the user uses a dynamic IP address, hackers can still retrieve the IP address.

Different Trojan programs were designed for different instant messaging clients. For example, with a user accounts and password stealing Trojans a hacker can have full control of the account once the user logs out. The hacker can thus perform various tasks like changing the password and sending the Trojan program to all of the user's contacts.

2.2 Phishing

The word phishing comes from the analogy that Internet scammers are using e-mail lures to fish for passwords and financial data from the sea of Internet users. The term was coined in 1996 by hackers who were stealing AOL Internet accounts by scamming passwords from unsuspecting AOL users. Since hackers have a tendency to replacing “f” with “ph” the term phishing was derived [11]. Phishing [12, 13] is a method that exploits people’s sympathy in the form of aid-seeking e-mails; the e-mail act as bait. These e-mails usually request their readers to visit a link that seemingly links to some charitable organization’s website; but in truth links the readers to a website that will install a Trojan program into the reader’s computer. Therefore, users should not forward unauthenticated charity mails, or click on unfamiliar links in an e-mail. Sometimes, the link could be a very familiar link or an often frequented website, but still, it would be safer if you’d type in the address yourself so as to avoid being linked to a fraudulent website. Phisher deludes people by using similar e-mails mailed by well-known enterprises or banks; these e-mails often asks users to provide personal information, or result in losing their personal rights; they usually contain a counterfeit URL which links to a website where the users can fill in the required information. People are often trapped by phishing due to inattention.

2.3 Fake Websites or Pharming

Fake bank websites stealing account numbers and passwords have become increasingly common with the growth of online financial transactions. Hence, when using online banking, we should take precautions like using a secure encrypted customer’s certificate, surf the net following the correct procedure, etc.

First, the scammers create a similar website homepage; then they send out e-mails with enticing messages to attract visitors. They may also use fake links to link internet surfers to their website. Next, the fake website tricks the visitors into entering their personal information, credit card information or online banking account number and passwords. After obtaining a user’s information, the scammers can use the information to drain the bank accounts, shop online or create fake credit cards and other similar crimes.

Similar in nature to phishing, pharming (Fake Websites) seeks to obtain personal or private (usually financial related) information through domain spoofing. Rather than being spammed with malicious and mischievous e-mail requests for you to visit spoof Web sites which appear legitimate, pharming ‘poisons’ a DNS server by infusing false information into the DNS server, resulting in a user’s request being redirected elsewhere. The victim’s browser however will show you are at the correct website, which makes pharming more serious and more difficult to detect. Whilst phishing attempts to scam people one at a time, pharming allows the scammers to target large groups of people at one time through domain spoofing [14].

2.4 Spoofing

A closely interconnected and often confused term with phishing and pharming is spoofing.

A “spoofed”, in Internet terms, is defined generally as the “cracker” who alters, or “forges,” an e-mail address, pretending to originate a message from a different source address than that which he or she truly has.

There are many ways an attacker may do this, and there are many types of attacks. The attacker may do this to gain access to a secured site that would accept the “hijacked” address as one of few permissible addresses, or more maliciously, the reason may be to hide the source of any type of attack. “Email spoofing is often an attempt to trick the user into making a damaging statement or releasing sensitive information (such as passwords).”

2.5 Spyware

Spyware is computer software that can be used to gather and remove confidential information from any computer without the knowledge of the owner. [15] Everything the surfer does online, including his passwords, may be vulnerable to spyware. Spyware can put anyone in great danger of becoming a victim of identity theft. Moreover, some forms of spyware can be installed on the computer from a remote location without the identity thief ever having physical access to the victim’s computer.

2.6 Electronic Bulletin Boards

Chat rooms and electronic bulletin boards have become breeding grounds for identity theft.

When criminals have obtained personal identifying information such as credit card numbers or social security numbers, they visit hacker chat rooms and post messages that they have personal information for sale.

2.7 Information Brokers

Information brokers have been around for decades, however, a new breed of information broker has emerged in recent years; the kind that sells personal information to anyone requesting it electronically via the Internet [16].

Driven by greed, some information brokers are careless when they receive an order. They fail to verify the identity of the requesting party and do little, if any, probing into the intended use of the information.

2.8 Internet Public Records

People search and genealogy websites have come under fire and some consumers are concerned that personal information online can be used to commit identity theft. Privacy advocates have become extremely concerned about the ease with which people can obtain personal information online.

2.9 Malicious Applications: Trojan Horses

In this context, a Trojan horse could be defined as an application that appears to be benign, but instead performs some type of malicious activity. [17] A Trojan can be disguised as a game, an e-mail attachment, or even a Web page. As soon as the victim runs or opens the camouflaged application, the Trojan installs itself on the hard drive and then runs each time Windows is started.

3. THE IMPACT OF HACKING ON INTERNET INFRASTRUCTURE

Internet infrastructure attacks can be broadly classified into the following four categories:

1. DNS Hacking Attacks
2. Routing Table Poisoning Attacks
3. Packet Mistreatment Attacks
4. Denial of Service Attacks

3.1 DNS Hacking Attacks

DNS attacks have illustrated the lack of authenticity and integrity of the data held within DNS as well as in the protocols that use host names as an access control mechanism.

The Impact of DNS Hacking

- **Denial of Service:** DoS is one of the most dangerous impacts of DNS hacking. DoS can be achieved in several ways: One way is to send back negative responses indicating that the DNS name does not exist. Another way is to redirect the client's request to a server that does not contain the service the client is requesting. DoS attacks on DNS servers can also achieve the same objective with greater effect.
- **Masquerading:** The adversary can use DNS attacks to redirect communication, and then masquerade as a trusted entity. If this is accomplished, an attacker can intercept, analyze, and/or intentionally corrupt the communications [18].
- **Information Leakage:** DNS threats also include leakage of information concerning internal networks to an attacker. Frequently, host names can represent project names that may be of interest revealing the operating system of the machine.
- **Domain Hijacking:** By compromising insecure mechanisms used by customers to update their domain registration information, attackers can take over the domain registration process to hijack legitimate domains.

3.2 Routing Table Poisoning Attacks

It is a challenging problem, because security was not introduced into the routing protocols from the start. It is important because the routing table forms the basis of the Internet, and any corruption of routing table may lead to significant consequences.

The Impact of Poisoning

- **Suboptimal Routing:** With the emergence of the Internet as a means of supporting soft real-time applications, optimality in routing assumes significant importance.

Routing table poisoning attacks can result in suboptimal routing that can affect real-time applications over the Internet.

- **Congestion:** Routing table poisoning can lead to artificial congestion if packets are forwarded to only certain portions of the network. Artificial congestion, thus created, is not solved by traditional congestion control mechanisms.
- **Partition:** It may result in the creation of artificial partitions in the network. This can become a significant problem since hosts residing in one partition will be unable to communicate with hosts residing in the other partition.
- **Overwhelmed Host:** Routing table poisoning may be used as a weapon for DoS attacks. If a router sends updates that result in concentration of packets to one or more selected servers, the servers can be taken out of service because of huge amounts of traffic. This type of DoS attack is more potent as the attacker is not spoofing identity, and is thus impossible to detect by the detection techniques mentioned in [19,20].
- **Looping:** The creation of triangle routing caused due to packet mistreatment attacks could also be simulated through improper updation of the routing table.
- **Access to Data:** Adversaries may gain illegal access to data through the routing table poisoning attack.

This may lead to adversaries snooping packets which were not supposed to pass through that part of the network.

3.3 Packet Mistreatment Attacks

This is an attack during data transmission phase, unlike the poisoning attack. Packet mistreating attacks have limited effectiveness compared to the routing table poisoning and DoS attacks. This is because the attacks are limited to a part of the network rather than the whole network as in the case of poisoning attacks. However, this type of attacks is possible and is very difficult to detect.

The Impact of Mistreatment

Though limited in their effectiveness, packet mistreatment attacks can result in:

- **Congestion:** Similar to poisoning, packet mistreatment attacks can also result in congestion in the network. Congestion is caused by misrouting the packets to heavily loaded links.
- **Lowering Throughput:** Mistreatment attacks can result in lowering of connection throughput. Malicious adversaries can prevent TCP packets from propagating further. The source, sensing congestion, lowers the sending window resulting in drop in connection throughput.
- **Denial-of-Service:** Packet mistreatment attacks can be used to indirectly cause DoS attacks by directing an uncontrollable number of packets toward a victim.

3.4 Denial-of-Service Attacks

In these sorts of attacks, the packets are routed correctly but the destination becomes the target of the attackers [21]. In a typical DoS attack, the attacker node spoofs its IP address and uses multiple intermediate nodes to overwhelm other nodes with traffic. DoS attacks are typically used to take important servers out of action for a few hours, resulting in DoS for all users served by the server. It can also be used to disrupt the services of intermediate routers.

The Impact of Denial-of-Service

- **UDP Flood:** UDP flooding is used by hackers to launch a DoS attack. For example, by sending UDP packets with spoofed return addresses, a hacker links one system's UDP character-generating service to another system's UDP echo service.
- **TCP/SYN Flood:** In this type of attack, the hacker sends a large volume of SYN packets to a victim. The return addresses of the packets are spoofed. Thus, the victim queues up SYN-ACKs but cannot continue sending them because it never receives ACKs from the spoofed addresses.
- **ICMP/Smurf:** In this type of attack, the hacker broadcasts ICMP ping requests with the return address spoofed to show the ultimate victim's address to a large group of hosts on a network. The hosts send their responses to the ultimate victim, whose system is overwhelmed and cannot provide service.

4. State-of-the-Art Technology for Information Security

The current state of affairs reveal that top high-tech technologies utilized for security purposes include: biometric applications, tokens, padded cells, cryptography and digital signature technologies etc.

4.1 Biometric Security Solutions

Biometrics is the study of measurable biological characteristics. In computer security, biometrics refers to authentication techniques that rely on measurable physical characteristics that can be automatically checked. There are several types of biometric identification schemes:

- Face:** The analysis of facial characteristics
- Fingerprint:** The analysis of an individual's unique fingerprints
- Hand geometry:** The analysis of the shape of the hand and the length of the fingers
- Retina:** The analysis of the capillary vessels located at the back of the eye
- Iris:** The analysis of the colored ring that surrounds the eye's pupil
- Signature:** The analysis of the way a person signs his name.
- Vein:** The analysis of pattern of veins in the back of the hand and the wrist
- Voice:** The analysis of the tone, pitch, cadence and frequency of a person's voice.

Though the field is not yet entirely developed, many scholars and scientists believe that biometrics will play a critical role in the future of security and especially in electronic commerce.

4.2 Honey Pot Decoys and Padded Cells

The anonymity of the Internet that allows identity thieves to hide conceals their true identity so effectively can be a double-edged sword used against them [22].

However, there is a drawback to this technique, as network users will discover the honey pot, and its effectiveness will be diminished.

Alternatively, they may use it for spoofing you with false attacks. You may wish to inform your trusted, legitimate users about the subterfuge with the intent of catching intruders, or you may wish to run a honey pot for a short period of time, then replace it with a new one with a different identity.

4.3 Tokens

No matter how secure a password system is, a clever identity thief can beat it. That is why many system owners now require use of tokens along with passwords. A token is a hardware or software device carried by, or in possession of, a computer user [23]. The token contain an electronically recorded and encrypted password.

Alternatively, it may have an on-board processor that can store and retrieve such a password when needed.

There are two categories of tokens:

- *Passive or Stored Value, e.g., bank card;
- *Active, e.g., one-time password generator.

The passive storage device is usually a magnetic stripe or smart card in which a static code word is stored.

Active tokens are higher end "secure" smart cards having a cryptographic processor. However, if they only store passwords or code words, but cannot perform processing functions, they are passive devices.

4.4 Cryptography

Although encryption is probably best known for protecting information from identity thieves, this application is probably overrated in business because of the colourful history of espionage, military and diplomatic concerns [24]. Cryptography has a variety of purposes and requires different kinds of key management for its three applications in communications, storage, and digital signatures.

In communications, communicators use cryptography to protect information in transit when it is particularly vulnerable (i.e., going through the cyberspace) because the senders and receivers typically do not have control over the communication route. This application requires short-term protection by encrypting the information before it is sent, and decrypting it upon arrival. Sender's systems may generate keys or receive keys from the intended receiver for short-term use.

5. Guidelines for Information Disclosure

(i) People are encouraged to request and use password-protected credit cards, and bank and phone accounts. To avoid using easily available information like their mother's maiden name, their birth date, the last four digits of their SSN, their phone number, or a series of consecutive numbers.

(ii) People must refrain from giving out their personal information on the phone, through emails, or over the Internet unless they have initiated the communication or are sure they know who they are dealing with.

Identity thieves are clever, and have posed as representatives of banks, Internet service providers (ISPs), and even government agencies to get people to reveal their SSN, mother's maiden name, account numbers, and other identifying information. Before consumers share any personal information, they must confirm that they are dealing with a legitimate organization.

(iii) People should be careful when storing their financial records, birth date, and bank account numbers on their computer, and should ensure that virus protection software should be updated regularly, and patches for the operating system and other software programs should be installed to protect against intrusions and infections that can lead to the compromise of their computer files or passwords. Ideally, virus protection software should be set to automatically update each week.

(iv) People are recommended to use firewall programs, especially if they use a high speed Internet connection like cable, DSL that leaves their computer connected to the Internet 24 hours a day. The firewall program will allow them to stop uninvited and unauthorized access to their computer.

(v) It is advisable not to open files sent from an unknown source or a stranger, or click on hyperlinks or download programs from untrustworthy sources. People should be careful about using file sharing programs. Opening a file could expose their system to a computer virus or a program known as “spyware”, which could capture their passwords or any other information as they type it [25].

(vi) Consumers and businesses are encouraged to use a secure browser and encryption software when entering into online transactions or sending their personal information to trusted sites.

(vii) Before disposing of a computer, people must delete all stored personal information and format their hard drive. Nevertheless, deleting files or reformatting the hard drive may not be enough because the files could still be retrieved from the computer’s hard drive. Thus, a “wipe” utility program could be used to overwrite the entire hard drive.

(viii) Accounts’ passwords should not be disclosed to anyone, as accounts can be hijacked, and people can find unexpected charges on their bills and statements.

(ix) Finally, beware of phishing, spoofing, spam attempts by being diligent, prudent, and skeptical about suspicious communications.

6. CONCLUSION

In the present paper, an overview of the problem of information security on internet has been made. Various hacking techniques have been elaborated and other technologies used for security of information have been discussed. In the field of information technology, there is always possibility for improvement and progress especially with respect to authentication, cryptography and privacy enhancing systems. As a step forward, certain ongoing projects like graphical password.

Enhanced Token and Multi-Modal Biometrics provide the provision of a higher level of security that minimizes the risk of hacking the identity on the internet. These tools are used in minimizing the risk and to make password more memorable to users and include multifunction smart cards that store multiple passwords on a single token.

Reference

[1] Galley, P. (1996, May 30). *Computer terrorism: What are the risks?* [English translation July 1, 1998 by Arif M. Janmohamed]. Retrieved November 2, 2003, from http://www.genevalink.ch/pgalley/infosec/sts_en/terrinfo.html.

[2] Schneier, B. (2000) *Semantic networks attacks*. *Communication of the ACM*, 43 (12), 168.

- [3] Janet J. Prichard and Laurie E. MacDonald Bryant University, Smithfield, RI, USA , “Cyber Terrorism: A Study of the Extent of Coverage in Computer Security Textbooks”, *Journal of Information Technology Education Volume 3*, 2004.
- [4] Anirban Chakrabarti and G. Manimaran, Iowa State University, “Internet Infrastructure Security: A Taxonomy”, *IEEE Network* •November/December 2002 0890-8044/02 © 2002 IEEE.
- [5] Tzer-Shyong Chen¹, Fuh-Gwo Jeng , and Yu-Chia Liu “Hacking tricks toward security on network environments”, *Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Computing, Applications and Technologies (PDCAT'06) 0-7695-2736-1/06* © 2006 IEEE.
- [6] http://www.symantec.com/region/tw/enterprise/article/icq_threat.html.
- [7] B. Schneier, “The trojan horse race,” *Communications of ACM*, Vol. 42, 1999, pp.128.
- [8] T. Tsuji and A. Shimizu, “An impersonation attack on one-time password authentication protocol OSPA,” to appear in *IEICE Trans. Commun*, Vol. E86-B, No.7, 2003.
- [9] C. L. Schuba, “Analysis of a denial of service attack on TCP,” *IEEE Security and Privacy Conference*, 1997, pp. 208-223.
- [10] G. Miklau, D. Suciu, “A formal analysis of information disclosure in data exchange,” *International Conference on Management of Data*, 2004, pp. 575-586.
- [11] Judge Mohamed CHAWKI and Dr. Mohamed S. ABDEL WAHAB “Identity Theft in Cyberspace: Issues and Solutions”, *Lex Electronica*, vol.11 n°1 (Printemps / Spring 2006)
- [12] E. Schultz, “Phishing is becoming more sophisticated,” *Computer and Security*, Vol. 24(3), 2005, pp. 184-185.
- [13] J. Hoyle, “‘Phishing’ for trouble,” *Journal of the American Dental Association*, Vol. 134(9), 2003, pp. 1182-1182.
- [14] <http://www.webopedia.com/TERM/p/pharming.html>
- [15] *Spywares PC Magazine* (N.Y., Wiley), [2005], p.8.
- [16] Identity Theft and Data Brokers (WTOP), available at <<http://www.wtopnews.com/?sid=434596&nid=97>>.
- [17] M. ERBSCHLOE, *Trojans, Worms and Spyware* (Oxford, Heinmann), [2005], p. 21.
- [18] Computer Emergency Response Team, “Multiple Vulnerabilities in BIND,” *CERT Advisory*, Nov. 1998.
- [19] H. Burch and B. Cheswick, “Tracing Anonymous Packets to their Approximate Sources,” *Proc. 2000 USENIX LISA Conf.*, Dec. 2000, 319–27.
- [20] G. Sager, “Security Fun with OCxmon and eflowd,” *Internet 2 Working Group Mtg.*, Nov. 1998.

Bibin & Om Prakash (2018) Review of Possible Threats and Solutions for Information Security on Internet

[21] K. J. Houle and G. M. Weaver, "Trends in Denial of Service Attack Technology," CERT Advisory, v1.0, Oct. 2001.

[22] J. WALLACE, *Nameless in Cyberspace: Anonymity on the Internet* (Cato Institute), [1999].

[23] ex., L. GORMAN, *Securing Business's Front Door; Password, Token and Biometric Authentication*

[24] ex., N. FERQUSON, *Practical Cryptography* (N.Y., John Wiley), [2003], p.8.

[25] P2P File Sharing, available at <http://www.ftc.gov/bcp/online/pubs/alerts/sharealrt.htm> also see Spyware, available at http://www.ftc.gov/bcp/online/pubs/alerts/spy_warealrt.htm.